

WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PHYSICS TEACHERS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this work, the need to form professional competence in the training of future physics teachers is substantiated. In addition, in the process of performing laboratory work on physics, the possibilities of forming professional competence of students are shown.*

Keywords: *physics, professional competence, creative thinking, teacher, specialist, process, laboratory, experiment.*

The introduction of new state educational standards based on the competency-based approach in our country imposes a number of urgent tasks on the teachers of higher education. In recent decades, increasing attention to the formation of abilities and competencies is not only about knowledge and skills, but also about personal qualities.

It is the result of the increasing demands to teachers, which emphasizes the priority of the competency-based approach as a specific type of concept and systematic understanding for describing the knowledge of a person.

Competency-based education (CBE) was started in the 1970s by the American philosopher, linguist and theorist N. Chomsky, but until now, different definitions and meanings of "competence" have been given, and researches are being conducted in educational areas. In order for pedagogical research to be effective, some authors define a research strategy by distinguishing three or four common aspects from the definitions and comments given to the concepts of "competence" and "communicative competence".

At the main "competences" symposium for Europe (Berk, Switzerland), the concept of "competence" was expressed by V. Hutmacher as follows: the concept of "competence" is side by side with such concepts as "performance", "ability", "mastery". At present, its content and essence have not been fully disclosed. The concept of "competence" is closer to the term "how I know" than the term "what I know". In institutions of higher education, it includes the important and multifaceted integration of the fundamentals of physical knowledge of students, the creation of various interdisciplinary connections, the integration of theoretical and practical materials, the study of general scientific methods and their active use in specific situations where research is important, the development of relevant skills and development of independence, initiative, loyalty, perseverance, as well as self-organization and self-management.

During the period of the students' involvement to a project related to the subject of physics in higher education institutions and later, engaged in scientific research, they have to carry out measurements and observations with the help of various devices in order to study the physical process. In order for such an activity to be effective, students should have the ability to determine which physical parameters in the studied process can be directly measured and to have the ability to work with measuring devices.

Laboratory work: is a practical training session conducted with the use of special devices (laboratory, technological, measuring instruments, a stand and a computer complex), and its main purpose is:

- to acquire the skills of using laboratory, technological and measuring devices.
- to have the ability to organize scientific-experimental research, such as conducting experiments, conducting observations or modeling to study and organize the characteristics of an object or process.

In addition to laboratory work, physical experiments are of great importance for students to learn physical phenomena and processes, because many physical theories and laws are based on educational physical experiments and explain the results of all physical experiments in the field of application.

By performing laboratory work and conducting physical experiments, the cognitive activity of students is activated, because the student must analyze the results obtained by conducting real experiments and make sure of their correctness by comparison. In addition, experimental results are the main tool for testing theoretical ideas and hypotheses and a source of new evidence.

- In the laboratory work, the subject statement, working formula, and the sequence of the work are prepared, and the students are only engaged in observation, measurement and calculation activities. Thanks to such activities, students mainly develop convergent thinking, but the characteristic of a person, creative thinking, which is essential for project activities, is less developed.

- In recommended laboratory works or physical experiments, students are required to determine mainly one physical quantity, i.e. free fall acceleration, conductor resistivity or fluid viscosity coefficient. This approach to laboratory works mainly develops students' methodological knowledge, but does not develop epistemic knowledge.

For the development of epistemic knowledge, the student needs to take a table or a graph of the dependence of the physical quantity characterizing the process on some other parameter and create new knowledge from it.

The opportunity to create and complete a physical task is more available in the "General Physics" course on mechanics, molecular physics, electricity and magnetism. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare several physical tasks related to these departments and give them to students as independent work.

In order to complete physical assignments, the student first familiarizes himself with the theoretical information on the subject relevant to the assignment and determines the problem, and then creates a physical problem based on this problem. The expression obtained for the analytical solution of this problem is considered a working formula, and the laboratory device is assembled based on it, determining the quantities that can be measured. Assembling a device requires finding unique original solutions, which, as we mentioned above, develops creativity in students. In order to make sure that the obtained result is correct, it is searched for comparison with table or internet data, it is analyzed and a conclusion is drawn.

From this point of view, in the laboratory work performed by physics bachelors in higher educational institutions, as we mentioned above, the method of finding almost one physical quantity is studied, so students can independently calculate physical quantities using graphs and

tables. Taking this into account, it is necessary to give students such a physical task that it is necessary to get some kind of graph or table during the performance of this task.

The content and essence of the formation of competence in physics consists of the following: mastering skills and knowledge infused with the idea of harmony between man and nature, deepening students' knowledge and developing their chemical thinking; understanding the unity of the world, the ability of scientific thinking, the desire to apply the ability of scientific thinking, acquired knowledge and skills to direct the formation of personal qualities, teaching and mastering knowledge in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

It is a set of systems that allow to organize teacher's pedagogical and students' cognitive activity harmoniously, to activate this activity, to use effective teaching methods, tools and forms, and to determine their interaction.

The student should be able to use and apply the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the field of physics in solving practical and theoretical problems encountered in his daily life, and at the same time, he must know the following competencies in the field of chemistry:

- observation of physical processes and phenomena: evaporation, condensation, aggregate state of matter, compression, properties of substances, combustion, liquefaction, melting, diffusion, recrystallization, sublimation, light, boiling, solidification, separation, melting, separation of colors and etc.

- explanation of physical processes and phenomena: the creation of physical phenomena, conditions of existence and conditions of occurrence, connection of this event with another event, explanation of processes and events.

- the ability to express physical formulas: formulas connecting laws with other laws, units of physical quantities (mass, volume, surface area, density, time), the ability to calculate errors in practice when solving experimental problems.

- the ability to work with physical substance, equipment and conduct experiments.

- the ability to choose equipment and tools, assemble and use them.

- the ability to write and summarize implementation conditions and results.

- applying physical knowledge in practice: being able to solve problems related to physical phenomena using learned concepts, rules, definitions, laws and formulas;

- practical application of acquired physical knowledge with the help of experiments;

In addition, the student controls a virtual laboratory or a computer model of a physical process, selects various parameters and, spending little time, gets enough information about the interrelationship of various parameters. One of the main achievements of the use of virtual laboratory and physical phenomena in education is that the student has a high chance of receiving this education independently.

As can be seen from the above, we will have the opportunity to form several competencies of future pedagogues by conducting experiments and laboratory work on physics.

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